

Studying Of Ethno Costumes Of Surkhondaryo And Specific Characteristics Of Using Elements In Modern Clothes

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Abstract: *The article studies the ethnic costumes of the Surkhondaryo and the use of elements in modern clothing. In the historical aspect, the regional features of the national women's clothing of the republic are considered.*

Keywords — costume, region, feature, embroidery, decoration, product length, color, decorative elements, outerwear, traditions.

INTRODUCTION.

In Surkhondaryo, there are many islands of ethnographic authenticity scattered through inaccessible mountain valleys. There is still a clear and socially significant division of the Uzbek ethnic group into tribes and clans. Each of them has its own recognizable traditional costume with a characteristic selection of fabrics, colors and ornaments, sets of jewelry. Even 20-30 years ago, on the streets of such regional centers as Baysun or Sherabad, one could meet many living carriers of this outgoing culture. One could learn a lot about her owner by her clothes: which area the woman was from, which tribe her family belonged to and how numerous it was, her marital status and social status, and even sometimes the number of children.[1]

The development of transport infrastructure and modern communications, high-tech mass production and extensive trade all over the world erase regional differences, unify not only fashion, but also everyday habits. Modern fashion design in Uzbekistan, of course, fruitfully feeds on national traditions, but inevitably loses those historical nuances that were inherent in the piece products of past times. The traditional women's costumes from grandmother's chests, unique in their beauty and originality, at best end up in museum exhibitions or to enthusiastic collectors.[1]

National dress is inextricably linked with the history of the nation, it reflects the national identity of the people, its material and spiritual values. Uzbek women's clothes are very diverse, colorful and attractive. According to the decorative design,

decorations, proportions of details, its color, saturation, and design features, national women's clothing can be conditionally divided into surkhan.[1]

Women's national clothes are as bright, festive and colorful as men's. The classic women's costume consists of a tunic dress and trousers, and a large number of jewelry is also a mandatory attribute.

Expensive fabrics embroidered with gold are used for festive dresses. A woman's headdress, in addition to a skullcap, also consisted of a turban and a headscarf so that women could keep their hair and hide their beauty from outsiders.

Traditional clothes have beautiful patterned embroidery, while each pattern is selected for a reason - it has both ethnic and magical meanings.[2]

They did not wear clothes in blue and black shades, but preferred red, blue and purple. The costume was complemented by spacious trousers, which were dressed under the dress and trimmed with colored braid - jiyak. As outerwear, women wore a mursak, a long loose robe. Ichigi or leather boots were worn on the feet, which were comfortable to wear. All rights reserved.[3]

Women's national clothes of the Surkhan region, depending on the age of the owner, had different widths, necklines and sleeve lengths of the dress. The women's costume consisted of a lower dress made of white fabric, over which casual upper dresses were worn.[4]

The clothes of the young girls of the Surkhan region differed from the women's mainly by the neckline of the dress. In a women's dress, the neckline was vertical with a stand-up collar or a turn-down collar. For young girls, the neckline was horizontal with a hole in the shoulder seam for easy entry of the head, which was tied with a ribbon.[5]

The clothes of Khorezmian women differed from the clothes of women in other regions by the originality of outerwear. Cotton winter robes were not quilted by hand, but were wrapped with a small stitch on a sewing machine. Cuts of 7-10 cm were made on the sleeves at the elbow level to roll up the ends of the sleeves during work.[6]

The cut of the traditional clothes of Bukhara and Samarkand women was different for different age groups and consisted of a tunic-shaped underdress. The sleeves of the lower dress with long and wide sleeves were usually decorated with embroidery at the bottom of the sleeve. In ancient times, this part of the shirt, called the "austin", was removed or removed for convenience during work.[7]

The length of the dress was ankle-length and the hem was wide. An upper dress was worn over the lower dress, also of a tunic-like cut, which was distinguished by a neckline. The collar of the girl's shirt was rounded, and the edges were decorated with a fabric of a different color. The collar was tied on both sides with ties or fastened with a button, and the neck in women's clothing was vertical, to which the collar was sewn.[8]

A distinctive feature of the dress of Bukhara women from the clothes of other regions was the presence of front embroidery, starting from the neckline and descending to the knee line. This embroidery was made with gold and silk threads. In the 50s and 60s of the XIX century, yoke dresses appeared in their clothes, which today they form the basis of the wardrobe of all Uzbek women.[8]

Picture-1. Traditional clothes of Surkhan women.

In the 60-70s of the last century, the style of clothing changed in two closely related directions. European-style clothing has become a tradition in cities and villages of Uzbekistan. The introduction of the features of European clothing into life has led to the fact that, along with national outfits, European-style clothing has taken a place in women's wardrobes.[9]

Historically, this has been associated with changing living conditions and the superiority of mass industrial production. At the same time, the forms of national dress also changed, determined by the climate and conditions of public life. The clothes of the national costume approached the proportions of the figure, women's dresses became narrower and shorter, the dresses that appeared earlier on the yoke, with turn-down collars, were preserved, but their sleeves became shorter.[10]

Over the past 30 years, the interest of Western fashion in Uzbek national fabrics, national embroidery and oriental style has been increasing. This phenomenon naturally affects the development of the fashion industry and the penetration of the national style. Given that Uzbek clothing is very colorful and diverse, you can see elements of national clothing created in the late XIX -early XX century, as well as the latest styles of clothing. Currently, the development of the art of modeling and fashion design in collaboration with artists is following a new path and this can be contemplated in the works of designers.[11]

The works of Uzbek fashion designers harmoniously combine national and international features. When creating modern models, Uzbek fashion designers are working to preserve the traditional national form of clothing using new technologies. An important role in the preservation of traditional national clothing is played by its combination with natural and climatic conditions, the mentality of the country and national traditions.[12]

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